

Advancing Robotic Palpation for Tumor Detection via Real-Time Tissue Viscoelastic Modeling with Collaborative Robotics

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Abstract—This long abstract introduces a new approach to the real-time estimation of body viscoelasticity parameters and penetration of the end effector during palpation exams using a collaborative robotic arm. The proposed estimator simplifies the nonlinear Hunt-Crossley model by utilizing the dimensionality reduction method. An extended Kalman filter is employed to enable online estimation by integrating the dynamic contact model. The algorithm is tested on various silicone samples, a material that mimics biological tissues, including those containing embedded hard inclusions to simulate cancerous cells within softer tissue.

I. INTRODUCTION

Palpation screening examinations are non-invasive and cost-effective procedures that can detect cancerous or other pathological conditions at an early stage when treatment is most effective. The efficacy of this method is contingent upon the examiner’s proficiency, particularly in the detection of minor or deeply situated abnormalities. The use of robotic palpation exams standardises the procedure, thereby reducing subjectivity and improving reliability. Furthermore, they facilitate access to examinations in regions where healthcare services are insufficient.

In recent years, several robotic palpation systems have been developed to detect solid bodies within soft tissues. These systems employ artificial tactile sensors and sensorised probes. A crucial element of these systems is the online estimation of tissue parameters, which is vital for the identification of stiffer regions. The deployment of analogous technology is of paramount importance in the context of robot-assisted minimally invasive surgery (RMIS), as it enables the provision of force feedback and the assurance of safe navigation along the body’s surface.

Different models estimate soft tissue properties, and the Hunt-Crossley (HC) model has proven superior in capturing the complexity of tissue contact [1]. However, existing methods for parameter estimation assume a known penetration depth, which is impractical in real-life medical exams [2], [3]. To address this, we propose a method that simultaneously estimates both penetration depth and model parameters using

We acknowledge the support of the MUR PNRR project FAIR - Future AI Research (PE00000013).

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dimensionality reduction techniques [4]. This eliminates the need for precise force sensors, improving system robustness and usability.

II. METHODS

This section introduces the contact models that are employed for the purpose of characterising the soft body. It then proceeds to present two estimation strategies, one that incorporates force sensing and one that does not. One straightforward approach to modelling the interaction between a rigid indenter and a deformable, viscoelastic body is the Kelvin-Voigt (KV) model. This model represents the force generated by the soft body as a parallel combination of a linear spring and a damper, as follows:

$$F_M(d) = \begin{cases} k_M d + c_M \dot{d}, & d \geq 0, \\ 0 & d < 0. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In this context, the notation $F_M(d)$ represents the force exerted by the material, with d denoting the penetration depth, and the variables k_M and c_M respectively signifying stiffness and damping. The velocity is given by the expression $v = \dot{d}$. The contact between an indenter of known shape and a soft body modelled as a viscoelastic material can be described using the dimensionality reduction method (DRM) [4]. In the context of DRM, the 3D forces between an axially symmetric indenter and a surface are calculated based on a 2D projection. The material is modelled as a series of parallel spring-damper elements, with a distance of Δx between each element. The deformation of each element is dependent on the contact point. In the case of a spherical indenter, the contact force on the end-effector is given by

$$F_M(d) = \begin{cases} \kappa d^{\frac{3}{2}} + \lambda d^{\frac{1}{2}} \dot{d}, & d \geq 0, \\ 0 & d < 0, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where the parameters κ and λ for an incompressible viscoelastic material are

$$\kappa = \frac{16G}{3}\sqrt{r}, \quad \lambda = 8\eta\sqrt{r}. \quad (3)$$

A. Online Estimation with Measured Force Inputs

The force acting on the end-effector of a robotic arm can be expressed in terms of the Kelvin-Voigt model as follows:

$$F_{FT} = k_M d + c_M \dot{d} + m_I \ddot{d},$$

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental setup: UR3e, a 6-axis force torque sensor BOTA SensorOne, a 3D printed indenter, and silicone specimens. (b) The 4 silicone types: S1 (ECOFLEX-0030), S2 (ECOFLEX-0030 + steel ball), S3 (Dragonskin-10NV), S4 (Dragonskin-10NV + steel ball).

leading to the state space model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{1,t+1} &= x_{1,t} + \Delta T x_{2,t} + w_1, \\
 x_{2,t+1} &= x_{2,t} + \frac{\Delta T}{m_I} (u_t - x_{1,t} x_{3,t} - x_{2,t} x_{4,t}) + w_2, \\
 x_{3,t+1} &= x_{3,t}, \\
 x_{4,t+1} &= x_{4,t}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $u_t = F_{FT}$.

For the nonlinear DRM model, the velocity update becomes:

$$x_{2,t+1} = x_{2,t} + \frac{\Delta T}{m_I} \left(u_t - x_{1,t}^{\frac{3}{2}} x_{3,t} - x_{1,t}^{\frac{1}{2}} x_{2,t} x_{4,t} \right) + w_2. \quad (5)$$

B. Online Sensorless Estimation with Force Approximation

For sensorless estimation, the force sensor can be substituted by the impedance law:

$$\ddot{d} = -\frac{1}{m_I + \Lambda_{33}} \left(\Lambda_{33} \ddot{z}_d + D_{33} \dot{z}_d + K_{33} \tilde{z} + (D_{33} + c_M) \dot{d} + k_M d \right). \quad (6)$$

leading to the discrete-time model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{2,t+1} &= x_{2,t} - \frac{\Delta T}{m_I + u_{4,t}} (u_{4,t} u_{3,t} + D_{33} u_{2,t} + K_{33} u_{1,t} \\
 &\quad + x_{3,t} x_{1,t} + (D_{33} + x_{4,t}) x_{2,t}) + w_{2,t}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The nonlinear DRM model update becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{2,t+1} &= x_{2,t} - \frac{\Delta T}{m_I + u_{4,t}} (u_{4,t} u_{3,t} + D_{33} u_{2,t} + K_{33} u_{1,t} \\
 &\quad + x_{1,t}^{\frac{3}{2}} x_{3,t} + x_{1,t}^{\frac{1}{2}} x_{2,t} x_{4,t} + D_{33} x_{2,t}) + w_{2,t}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experimental Setup and Silicone Materials

This study assesses the feasibility of utilising an estimation algorithm to determine the penetration, stiffness, and damping of soft bodies made of silicone materials. An impedance controller is employed with a sinusoidal desired trajectory:

$$z_d(t) = z_0 + z_1 \sin(4\pi t) + z_2 \sin(8\pi t). \quad (9)$$

The experiments utilized a 6-DoF position-controlled robotic arm (UR3e) as shown in Fig. 1a. Two types of silicone were used: Dragonskin-10NV (stiffer, muscle-like) and ECOFLEX-0030 (softer, fat-like). Silicone specimens were created using a standardized molding process. Specimens with a metal sphere (9 mm diameter) were also fabricated to simulate stiffer cancerous tissue. Silicone samples are labeled as in Fig. 1b, i.e., S1 to S4. For consistency, the same filter initial condition, $\hat{x}_0 = [1, 1, 0, 0]$, and covariance matrix, P_0 , were used in all tests.

B. Force Reconstruction

The feasibility of reconstructing forces using estimated parameters without a force sensor is analyzed. After an initial 30 ms, models M_2 and M_4 estimate the force with an absolute error of 0.4 N. The mean squared error (MSE) from 5 s to 10 s is 0.0614 N^2 for M_2 and 0.0559 N^2 for M_4 . Despite incorrect values, M_2 effectively tracks the force on the end-effector, suggesting that accurate force determination is possible without a sensor.

C. Tumour Identification

The palpation was done on each silicon. As expected, models M_1 and M_2 do not converge to the correct stiffness, but slight parameter variations between silicones with and without the steel ball suggest potential foreign mass detection. In contrast, models M_3 and M_4 exhibit slower dynamics but converge to correct stiffness and damping values, successfully detecting the silicone with the metal ball. Impedance-based models M_2 and M_4 tend to underestimate stiffness due to the approximation of the control law. Nevertheless, the estimated values are still sufficient to differentiate materials.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that soft tissue properties and end-effector penetration can be effectively estimated using dimensionality reduction and an extended Kalman filter. The approach permits the estimation of force without the necessity for supplementary sensors, thereby facilitating rapid filter convergence and precise parameter estimation. Consequently, it is particularly well-suited to applications requiring rapid contact detection. Furthermore, the method demonstrates the capacity to identify stiffer bodies within soft materials. In conclusion, the work demonstrates considerable promise and paves the way for further research that will facilitate the development of a more reliable and useful framework.

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